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A SHORT REVIEW ON CANAVAN DISEASE

G.V.K.S.Abhinav

Koringa College of Pharmacy, Kakinada, Andhra Pradesh, India.

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ABSTRACT

It is a rare genetic neurological disorder characterised by the spongy degeneration of the white matter in the brain. Canavan affects at birth. The affected newborn may look normal at birth, but they usually develop symptoms between 3-6 months of age. The symptoms of canavan disease include an abnormally large head, lack of head control, severely diminished muscle tone resulting in floppiness, and delay in reaching developmental sitting and walking. Most affected children develop lifethreatening complications by 10 years of age. The cause of the rare disorder includes mutations in the aspartoacylase gene that affects the breakdown of N-acetylaspartic acid (NAA). It is inherited as an autosomal recessive condition. This disease affects men and women equally. The disorder affects all ethnic groups, but happens with greater frequency in individuals of Ashkenazi Jewish descent. The carrier frequency in Ashkenazi Jewish is estimated to be high as one in 40-58 people. The risk for an affected child born to Ashkenazi Jewish parents is between 1 in 6,400 and 1 in 13,456. Diagnosis of canavan disease may be suspected in infants with the characteristic finding of the disorder. It may be confirmed by a thorough clinical evaluation, a detailed patient history, and a variety of specialized tests. The tests may include gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, a device that can detect elevated levels of NAA in the urine. Elevated levels of NAA can also be detected in the blood and cerebrospinal fluid. Patient registry is the canavan disease patient insight network (PIN) is a shared network that collects experience directly from patients and families. PIN services to create a research ready community that can help drug developers and researchers get closer to the patients.

Corresponding author

G.V.K.S.Abhinav

II/VI doctor of pharmacy,
Koringa College of pharmacy,
Kakinada,
Andhra Pradesh, India.
2402abhinav@gmail.com
9885086574

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INTRODUCTION

It is a rare genetic neurological disorder characterised by the spongy degeneration of the white matter in the brain. Canavan affects at birth. By the absence of vital enzymes known as aspartoacylase (ASPA). Aspartoacylase breaks N-acetylaspartic acid (NAA) into building blocks essential for building myelin [1]. This disease has been classified as one of a group of genetic disorders known as the leukodystrophies. The disease was named for Myrtille Canavan who first described the disorder in 1931. She was one of the first female pathologists and well known for Canavan. In the year 1993 Dr. Ruben Matalon discovered the gene that causes Canavan from the tissues provided by the several Canavan families [3]. Anyone can be the carrier for the Canavan disease, if both parents are the carriers, each child has a 25% of having the disease. Ashkenazi Jews are at high risk. Babies with this disease may appear normal at birth time but typically develop normally for several months. Sometimes symptoms are noticeable at birth. The main cause for Canavan disease was the absence of a vital enzyme called aspartoacylase (ASPA). Myelin is a fatty membrane that forms a protective coating. There are some diagnosing tests like combination of biochemical and DNA tests.

Other clinical names for Canavan disease are Aspartoacylase Deficiency, Spongy Degeneration of the Brain, Van Bogaert Spongy Degeneration of the Brain [5].

History :

Canavan disease was first discovered in the year 1931 by Myrtille Canavan. She co-wrote a paper discussing the case of a child, who died at 16 months old and whose brain had a spongy white section. It was first to identify this degeneration discovered of the central nervous system, which is later named as Canavan disease. In the year 1993 Dr. Ruben Matalon discovered the gene that causes Canavan from the tissue provided by several Canavan families [2].

Symptoms :

The symptoms of the disease can vary greatly. Most common symptoms are poor head and neck control, larger than normal head circumferences, reduced visual responsiveness and tracking, seizures, difficulty sleeping, eating, unusual posture, with legs often kept straight and arms flexed, unusual muscle tone, leading to stiffness. Reduced visual responsiveness and tracking [4]. Canavan disease symptoms may worsen sometimes. For example, the first sign is a baby with Canavan disease may appear normal at birth and typically develops normally for several months. As its development was slow, parents may notice a reduction in vision and tracking. Gradual loss of skills one by one, and unable to crawl, turn over, sit or reach out. Loss of coordination, inability to swallow and difficulty breathing. By age of 3 and beyond, children lose muscle tone and function. Some children experience recurrent seizures [6].

Diagnosis :

By an MRI or CT shows the signs of decreased myelination leads to the Canavan diagnosis. Anyone can be carrier of the disease, when both parents are carriers each has 25% of having the disease. It is diagnosed through a combination of biochemical and DNA tests. Increased amounts of N-acetylaspartic acid if found in the urine. Deficiency of aspartoacylase is found in cultured skin fibroblasts. Known disease causing mutations are frequently found through DNA testing [9].

Treatment :

Canavan disease causes progressive brain atrophy. There is no cure, nor is there a standard course of treatment. Treatment is symptomatic and supportive. It may include provision of adequate nutrition and hydration, treatment of infectious diseases, and protection of the airway. Physical therapy is to minimize contractures and maximize motor abilities and sitting posture. Gastrostomy can help to maintain adequate food intake and hydration when swallowing difficulties. Seizures are treated with antiepileptic drugs [8].

Prognosis :

The prognosis is poor. Death usually occurs before age 10, although some children may survive into their teens and twenties.

Research :

Research is being done on canavan disease. It has been located. Laboratories offer prenatal screening for this disorder to populations at risk. Scientists have developed animal models for this disease and they are developing therapeutic strategies. Three strategies are currently under investigation, gene transfer to the brain in order to replace the mutated gene for the enzyme, metabolic therapy to provide a crucial missing metabolite, and enzyme therapy the enzyme aspartoacylase is engineered to be able to enter the brain and is injected in the bloodstream. The results were obtained using these strategies [7].

Patient registry is the canavan disease patient insight network (PIN) is a shared network that collects experience directly from patients and families. PIN services to create a research ready community that can help drug developers and researchers get closer to the patients.

DISCUSSION

Canavan disease is a rare genetic neurological disorder characterized by the spongy degeneration of the white matter in the brain. Affected infants may appear normal at birth, but usually develop symptoms between 3-6 months of age. Symptoms may include an abnormally large head, lack of head control, severely diminished muscle tone resulting in floppiness, and delays in reaching developmental milestones such as independent sitting and walking. Most affected children develop life-threatening complications by 10 years of age. Canavan disease occurs because of mutations in the aspartoacylase (ASPA) gene that affects the breakdown (metabolism) of the N-acetylaspartic acid (NAA). It is inherited as an autosomal recessive condition. Canavan disease belongs to a group of disorders known as the leukodystrophies. The leukodystrophies are a group of rare, progressive, metabolic, genetic disorders that can affect the brain, spinal cord and often the nerves outside the central nervous system. Each type of leukodystrophy is caused by an abnormality affecting a specific gene that results in abnormal development of one of at least 10 different chemicals that make up the white matter of the brain. The white matter is tissue composed of nerve fibers. Many of these nerve fibers are covered by a collection of fats (lipids) and proteins known as myelin. Myelin, which collectively may be referred to as the myelin sheath, protects the nerve fibers, acts as an insulator and increases the speed of transmission of nerve signals. Each type of leukodystrophy affects a different part of the myelin sheath, leading a range of different neurological problems.

CONCLUSION

We suggest the research done on canavan disease, their diagnosing tests like MRI or CT scan. It is a rare genetic neurological disorder characterised by the spongy degeneration of the white matter in the brain. Canavan affects at birth. The affected newborn may look normal at birth, but they usually develop symptoms between 3-6 months of age. The symptoms of canavan disease include an abnormally large head, lack of head control, severely diminished muscle tone resulting in floppiness, and delay in reaching developmental sitting and walking. Most affected children develops lifethreatening complications by 10 years of age. It may be confirmed by a thorough clinical evaluation, a detailed patient history, and a variety of specialized tests. The tests may include gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, a device that can detect elevated levels of NAA in the urine. Elevated levels of NAA can also be detected in the blood and cerebrospinal fluid.

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REFERENCES

1. Canavan disease review, Wednesday, 19 October 2016 11:30
<https://www.ntsad.org/index.php/canavan>
2. Canavan disease
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Canavan_disease#cite_note-11
3. Canavan disease information page
<https://www.ninds.nih.gov/Disorders/All-Disorders/Canavan-Disease-Information-Page>
4. What is canavan disease and how is it treated ?
<https://www.healthline.com/health/canavan-disease#symptoms>
5. Canavan disease clinical names
<https://ulf.org/canavan-disease/>
6. Merrill ST, Nelson GR, Longo N, Bonkowsky JL. Cytotoxic edema and diffusion restriction as an early pathoradiologic marker in Canavan disease: Case report and review of the literature. Orphanet J Rare Dis 2016;11:169.
7. Canavan disease research
https://www.medicinenet.com/canavan_disease/article.htm#is_there_any_treatment_for_canavan_disease
8. Treatment for canavan disease
<https://rarediseases.info.nih.gov/diseases/5984/canavan-disease>
9. Canavan disease discussion
<https://rarediseases.org/rare-diseases/canavan-disease/>

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